

IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE INFLAMMATORY PROCESS IN HEMOCOLITIS SYNDROME IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. Hemocolitis syndrome (HS) in children represents a severe pathology associated with inflammatory processes in the intestines and activation of the immune response. This study is dedicated to analyzing the immune mechanisms involved in the development of acute diarrheal syndrome with hemocolitis in children aged 6 months to 7 years. The examined indicators of the non-specific immune response and cytokine profile reveal significant changes in both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. The obtained results demonstrate the activation of the inflammatory process in children with HS and may be useful for developing new therapeutic approaches.

Keywords: hemocolitis, immune response, cytokines, pediatric gastroenterology, inflammation, CRP, IL-6, IFN- γ , VEGF-A, immunopathogenesis.

Аннотация. Синдром гемоколита (СГ) у детей представляет собой серьезную патологию, связанную с воспалительными процессами в кишечнике и активацией иммунного ответа. Настоящее исследование посвящено анализу иммунных механизмов, задействованных в развитии острого диарейного синдрома с гемоколитом у детей в возрасте от 6 мес- до 7 лет. Изученные показатели неспецифического иммунного ответа и цитокиновый профиль, позволяют выявить значительные изменения как в провоспалительных, так и в противовоспалительных механизмах. Полученные результаты демонстрируют активацию воспалительного процесса у детей при СГ и могут быть полезны для разработки новых подходов к терапии.

Ключевые слова: гемоколит, иммунный ответ, цитокины, детская гастроэнтерология, воспаление, СРБ, ИЛ-6, ИФН- γ , VEGF-A, иммунопатогенез.

Annotatsiya. Bolalarda gemokolit sindromi (GS) ichaklardagi yallig'lanish jarayonlari va immun javobning faollashuvi bilan bog'liq og'ir patologiya hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot 6 oylikdan 7 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda gemokolit bilan kechuvchi o'tkir diareya sindromining rivojlanishida ishtirok etuvchi immun mexanizmlarni tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Nospetsifik immun javob va sitokin profili ko'rsatkichlari tahlili yallig'lanish jarayonlarining pro-yallig'lanish va anti-yallig'lanish mexanizmlaridagi sezilarli o'zgarishlarni aniqladi. Olingan natijalar GS bilan kasallangan bolalarda yallig'lanish jarayonining faollashganligini ko'rsatadi va yangi terapevtik yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishda foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: gemokolit, immun javob, sitokinlar, bolalar gastroenterologiyasi, yallig'lanish, CRP, IL-6, IFN- γ , VEGF-A, immunopatogenez.

Introduction. Immune mechanisms play a key role in the development and severity of inflammatory reactions in the intestines. Disruptions in cellular and humoral immunity, as well as changes in cytokine levels, can exacerbate the inflammatory process, leading to tissue damage and systemic complications. Hemocolitis syndrome (HS) in young children is a pressing issue in infectious disease medicine, pediatric gastroenterology, and immunology. The disease is

characterized by inflammatory changes in the intestines, resulting in mucosal damage and systemic complications [1,2,3].

Research on the immune response in children with HS is particularly important in the age group of 6 months to 7 years, a critical period for immune system development, as identified by J.V. Solomon. Studies show that in acute diarrhea (AD), hyperactivation of the immune system leads to intestinal mucosal damage and severe inflammatory changes [4,5]. Given the increasing prevalence of intestinal infections and bacterial resistance to traditional antibiotics, understanding immune responses in these conditions is essential for developing new treatments to effectively control inflammation and prevent complications.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1.

Parameters of non-specific immune factors in children with HS

Indicator	Control group (n=25)	Mild HS (n=25)	Moderate HS (n=95)
CRP (mg/L)	3.51±1.42	9.83±1.78**	15.61±3.22***
PCT (ng/mL)	0.25±0.17	0.64±0.43^	0.89±0.61^

*Significance levels: *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001. ^ Non-significant values compared to control group.

The analysis of results indicates that in children with mild HS, CRP levels increased by 2.8 times (P<0.01), indicating active inflammation. In moderate HS, CRP levels were 4.5 times higher (P<0.001), confirming a severe inflammatory process. PCT levels also increased by 2.5 and 3.6 times, respectively; however, statistical significance was not observed (P>0.05).

Table 2.

Serum cytokine levels in children with HS

Indicator (pg/mL)	Control group (n=25)	Mild HS (n=25)	Moderate HS (n=95)
IL-4	2.39 ±0.87	5.86 ±0.49***	1.63 ±1.47^
IL-6	3.51±1.93	7.03±0.45*	9.28±1.39**
IFN-γ	12.59±2.18	21.68±2.51**	25.01±1.71***
VEGF-A	169.57±16.87	320.29±30.09***	390.57±19.57***

*Significance levels: *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001.

Analysis of cytokine profiles showed significant alterations in cytokine levels in children with HS. IL-6 levels were twice as high (P<0.05) in mild cases and 2.6 times higher (P<0.01) in moderate HS cases compared to the control group. IFN-γ levels increased by 1.7 times (P<0.01) in mild cases and by 2 times (P<0.001) in moderate HS cases.

Interestingly, IL-4 levels increased significantly in mild HS cases (2.45 times, P<0.001) but decreased in moderate HS cases by 31.8%, dropping below the control group level (P>0.05). VEGF-A levels also increased significantly in both mild and moderate cases, indicating its role in tissue repair and inflammation modulation.

Conclusions

1. The immunopathogenesis of hemocolitis syndrome in children with acute diarrhea is associated with a severe imbalance in pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory mechanisms, as reflected in elevated levels of CRP, IL-6, IFN-γ, and VEGF-A.

2. Combining analyses of innate humoral factors, such as CRP and PCT, with cytokine profiling provides a deeper understanding of inflammation in HS.

3. The studied biomarkers can be used to predict inflammation severity and develop more targeted therapeutic approaches aimed at balancing pro- and anti-inflammatory mechanisms.

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